

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MOM****FIRST NAME: ROMMY****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1

The author used MSWord 2018 on Windows 11

QUIZ FOR INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING (DOCTORATE) COURSE

1. The Chicago Manual of Style is focused on book publishing, so it has few instructions to offer for formatting papers. What then guides writers who apply the Chicago style in writing?
 - Turabian's Manual for Writers is the official guide to applying the Chicago style to term papers, theses, and dissertations.¹**
 - Chicago Style Manual used by researchers is the official guide to applying the Chicago style to term papers, theses, and dissertations.
 - European English Guide for Chicago style for papers, theses, and dissertations.
 - Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. Euclid Citation Guide is the final manuscript to apply the Chicago style in writing.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 50.

2. According to Cleenwerck and Gulma, each paragraph in the body of the essay should deal with one main point/ aspect to capture the subject of the essay. What, then, should each paragraph contain?²
- The group of sentences containing the subject of the sentence, Object, and verb of the sentence
 - A topic sentence that states the main or controlling idea; supporting sentences to explain and develop the point you are making; evidence and analysis.**
 - The main sentence that explains the goal or essence of the write-up and a concluding sentence that captures the hypothesis and the conclusion drawn from findings.
 - An outline of the key points, topics, issues, ideas, or other information, as appropriate.
3. Sources of information/works to conduct research are conventionally categorized into three kinds; what are they?³
- Primary, Secondary, and Tertiary**
 - First, second, and Thirdhand
 - Internet sources, Books and Journals
 - Consult Reference Work, Explore Online Database and Search the Library Catalog.

² Ibid., 11.

³ Kate L. Turabian. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th ed. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. Fitz Gerald, and the University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 32.

4. According to Turabian, “every project involves countless specific tasks, so it is easy to get overwhelmed. But in all research projects, you have just five general aims”. What are the five general aims?⁴

Ask a question worth answering; find an answer that can be supported with good reasons; find good data that be used as reliable evidence to support reasons; draft an argument that makes a good case to justify the answer and revise that draft until readers think the first four goals have been met.

Develops better insight into the topic; enhance the research quality aids in decision-making and inculcates logical and systematic thinking to achieve the first four objectives.

Derive better solutions and provides systematic structure to generate measurable and testable data, gradually adding to the accumulation of human knowledge and enhancing the quality of findings.

Find good data that be used as reliable evidence to support reasons; enhance the research quality aids in decision making, derive better solutions and provides systematic structure.

5. A citation style used widely in most social sciences and the natural and physical sciences is the author-date style, so called because the author's name and publication date are critical for identifying sources. What is the format for Turabian Single Author or Editor style of citation of a Book?⁵

⁴ Ibid., 23.

⁵ Ibid., 229.

- Author's Last Name, Author's First Name. Year of Publication. Title of Book: Subtitle of Book. Place of Publication: Publisher's Name.**
- Author's First and Last Names, "Title of Article: Subtitle of Article," Title of Journal Volume Number, Issue Number (Date of Publication): XX.
- Author's First and Last Names, Title of Book: Subtitle of Book (Place of Publication: Publisher's Name, Date of Publication), XX
- Author's First Name, Author's Last Name. Year of Publication. Title of Book: Subtitle of Book. Place of Publication: Publisher's Name.
6. Experienced researchers understand that genuine research must matter not only to the researcher but also to others. In achieving this, experienced researchers have developed a particular formula as a guide. What is the formula?⁶
- XYZ (Topic; Question and Significance) Topic: I am working on X; Question: because I want to find out Y; Significance: so that I can help others understand Z.**
- ABC (Aims; Questions and Methodology) Aim: I am working to achieve A: because I want to find out about B, so that I can understand how to achieve C.
- XYZ (Research questions; Objectives and Findings): Research Questions; I want to find out about X; Objectives: so that I can achieve Y and come to a conclusion regarding Z.
- ABC (Question, Significance and Aims); Question: because I want to find out A; Significance: so that I can help others understand B; Aim: in order to achieve C.

⁶ Ibid., 20.

7. The various legal acts adopted under the Treaties form the European Union's 'secondary legislation. Article 288 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union specified chiefly of what?⁷

Regulations, Directives, and Decisions

Rules, Directives, and Conclusions

Guidelines, Commands, and Results

Protocols, Orders, and Decisions

8. According to Turabian, citation styles differ in the elements included and in the format. However, they have the same aim: to give readers the information they need to identify and find a source. What questions must be answered in order to properly cite work and provide information about the source of information?⁸

Who was responsible for creating the source? What title or other data identifies it? Who published it? When? Where can it be found?

What year was the work published? What issue does the work address? What relevance is the source to the present research?

Who are the authors? What kind of source is it? What is the title of the work, and What year was it published?

How relevant is the source to the research? What kind of source is it? Who authored it? What is the title?

⁷ European Commission. *English Style Guide a Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. 7th eds. Alexander Daniel et al. (European Commission, 2022), 77.

⁸ Kate L. Turabian, 141.

9. The Road Map for Conducting a good Literature Review requires which of the following steps? ⁹

- Identify and retrieve literature; review and critically analyze literature synthesis: write the review and develop and present a theoretical or conceptual framework.**
- Find the literature sources, cite the literature, and determine the year of publication and the major highlights of the literature.
- Look for essential components in the literature.; extract and record information by asking systematic questions of the literature and develop an analytic format and use it consistently.
- Identify themes and translate them into corresponding headings and subheadings; write the first draft; ensure that your argument flows logically and coherently, that it is written clearly, and that citations support it well; test the draft by inviting/soliciting feedback from colleagues and advisors and edit, revise, and refine, incorporating feedback from others.

10. What are the four core paradigms that inform qualitative research?¹⁰

- Foundationalism, Poststructuralism, Postmodernism, and Posthumanism.

⁹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation, A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth ed. (Columbia University: SAGE Publications Ltd., 2019), 363.

¹⁰ Ibid., 146-150.

- Postpositivism, Pragmatism, Social Constructivism/Interpretivism and Critical theory.**
- Positivism, Postpositivism, postmodernism and Posthumanism.
- Poststructuralism, Critical theory, Foundationalism and Pragmatism.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
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